

Clinical Profile and Outcome of Patients in Obstetric ICU in Tertiary Care Centre in BiharAnamika¹, Pushpa²^{1,2}Senior Resident Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PMCH, Patna, Bihar, India.

Received: 20-06-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 12-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Pushpa

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Objective: Though pregnancy and labor are considered a physiological process the potential for catastrophic complications is constant and may develop in a matter of minutes. One indicator of pronounced maternal morbidity is obstetric admission into the ICU. This study was done to evaluate the risk factors and maternal and fetal outcome of ICU admissions.

Materials and Methods: This was a retrospective study done in 6 bedded ICU, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, PMCH, Patna, Bihar over a period of 2 yrs from January 2017 to December 2018. Analysis of the causes of obstetric ICU admission, interventions required, duration of ICU stay and maternal and fetal outcome done.

Results: Out of total 17147 labour room admissions 2139 patients were admitted in ICU. Patients of eclampsia / HDP had maximum occupancy followed by obstetric haemorrhage. 238 patients died while 1891 survived 10 patients were taken to other hospital, by patient's relatives. Mean duration of ICU stay was 5.8 days. Perinatal death was 21.55%

Conclusion: The major cases admitted in ICU were of Antepartum eclampsia/HDP, pregnancy with heart disease, obstetrics haemorrhage, septic abortion, severe anaemia and severe jaundice with pregnancy. Multiparity, lack of ANC, delayed reporting to hospital were the major risk factors associated and also influencing the maternal and fetal outcome.

Keywords: Obstetric ICU, Critically Ill Obstetric Patients, Eclampsia, Obstetric Haemorrhage, Maternal Mortality.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Admission to obstetric ICU is an important indicator of maternal morbidity. [1,2] Critically ill obstetric patients represent an interesting group with unique characteristics, whose management is challenged by the presence of a fetus, an altered maternal physiology and disease specific to pregnancy. [3]

Annually, 287,000 women die in pregnancy or childbirth, 4.9 million children die of largely preventable causes before their 5th birthday, and there are 1.9 million stillbirths. Most of these deaths are linked to preventable or treatable conditions, and can largely be averted with access to timely, high quality health care services. [4]

Direct obstetrical causes as well as diseases aggravated by physiological alterations in pregnancy all lead to ICU admission and also influence outcome.

WHO defines maternal mortality as "Death of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of duration and site of pregnancy, from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management but

not from accidental or incidental causes. [5] "Severe acute maternal morbidity" (SAMM) is more common than maternal mortality and is defined as "a woman who nearly died but survived a complication that occurred during pregnancy, childbirth or within 42 days after termination of pregnancy".[2] The clinical and demographic profile of SAMM cases shares many characteristics with cases of maternal mortality.[6,7] So women at risk must be identified and managed appropriately.

Perinatal mortality is defined by WHO as number of stillbirths and deaths in the 1st week of life. An attempt has also been made to understand the cause of maternal death among the ICU admitted patients. Current maternal mortality in India is 130 per 100000 live births. Obstetric ICU admission constitute 0.4-4% to total ICU admissions in government (public) hospitals.

Material and Method

This is a prospective, observational, descriptive study conducted at obstetric ICU (6 bedded) in PMCH (a tertiary care medical college and hospital)

from period of January 2017 to December 2018. The protocol for the study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the hospital.

Inclusion Criteria: All pregnant women and postpartum patients within 6wks of delivery needing ICU care were included in study.

Exclusion Criteria: Non obstetric female patients admitted to the ICU for either gynaecological or medical or surgical causes.

After admission to ICU, a detailed history was taken from relatives of the patient and also extracted from available medical records. Basic demographic variables (age, parity, literacy level, socioeconomic

status) of the patient were recorded. No. of antenatal visits, ICU stay duration, pre-existing medical disorder, complications of present pregnancy, mode of delivery, maternal and fetal outcome. Causes of maternal mortality were also recorded.

The results are presented in frequencies, percentages, and mean ± standard deviation as deemed appropriate.

Results

Table 1: 2139 (12.47%) patients were admitted in ICU out of total 17147 labour room admissions in 2 year period.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics.

167 (7.81%)	G1	303 (14.16%)	P1	49 (2.29%)	No Anc	186 (8.69%)	<12	158 (7.38%)
806 (37.66%)	G2	374 (17.48%)	P2	71 (3.32%)	<3	1376 (64.33%)	12-24	41 (1.92%)
1166 (54.51%)	G3	318 (14.86%)	P3	53 (2.48%)	>3	577 (26.97%)	25-28	135 (6.31%)
	³ G4	738 (34.50%)	³ P4	233 (10.89%)			29-32	297 (13.88%)
							33-37	176 (8.23%)
							³ 37	926 (43.29%)
							Postpartum	406 (18.98%)

Table 2: Cause of OBS ICU admission

387	18.09%
148	6.91%
119	5.56%
21	0.98%
43	2.01%
172	8.04%
212	9.91%
27	1.26%
Anaemia	199 9.303%
Jaundice/hepatic encephalopathy	209 9.77%
ARF	24 1.12%
Cerebrovascular haemorrhage	8 0.37%
heart disease/CHF	42 1.96%
Others	87 4.06%
13	0.60%

Table 3: Maternal outcome

	5.8 days	
	1891	84.19%
	238	11.12%
	10	0.46%
	1317	61.57%
	574	26.83%
	1815	84.85%

vaginal delivery occurred in 840 patients, patients underwent emergency LSCS in 547 cases, emergency laparotomy was done in 344 patients while rest were managed medically.

Table 4: causes of death in ICU

	68(28.57%)
	37(15.55%)
	34(14.28%)
	18(7.56%)
	16(6.72%)
	6(2.5%)
	24(10.08%)
	27(11.34%)
	4(1.68%)
	4(1.68%)

Fetal outcome 876(40.95%) babies were born healthy at term. Perinatal death was 461(21.55%). Rest were preterm /lbw babies who needed NICU admission.

Discussion

Analysis of the data in our study shows that 2139 of a total of 17,147 obstetric patients required ICU that accounts for about 12.47% admission rate which was significantly higher than studies conducted by Rathod et al & Gupta et al and several other national and developed world data.

This study was conducted at govt medical college PMCH at Bihar which mostly serves the rural and poor population which explains the late reporting to medical care facility and hence a delayed and increased need of ICU admission.

In our study we found that maximum patients admitted were in the age group of >30yrs (51%), in the late third trimester (51.52%) similar to that seen in study done by Rathod et al.

Most of our patient were multigravida (49.36%) and were admitted in antepartum period. In contrast to what was found in the study conducted by Rathod et

al, Khan et al and Gupta et al where most ICU admissions were due to complication that developed in postpartum period. [9,10]

We also found that maximum ICU admissions were seen in patients with < 3 ANC visits (73.02%).

51.2% Patients admitted in third trimester and 43.29% in late 3rd trimester which is comparable to Bhadade et al (41%) [11,12]

Thus advanced maternal age and multiparity and fewer antenatal visits were found to be associated with visibly higher complications and more ICU admissions.

Most common condition requiring ICU admission in our study was found to be PIH(20.09%) followed by obstetric haemorrhage(18.09%) similar to that found in a study conducted by Bhadade et al[12] hypertension (PIH) (14.75%), obstetrical hemorrhage (4%) and puerperal sepsis (2.45%) in contrast to studies conducted by Gupta et al.[9], Khan et al [11] where obstetric haemorrhage was found to be the leading cause .

Other causes that contributed significantly were rupture uterus & obstructed labour (10.05%), sepsis

(9.91%), jaundice (9.77%), severe anemia (9.303%), rupture ectopic(6.9%), IUFD(5.56%).

Obstetrical haemorrhage was high in multiparous patient and patient with previous surgical obstetrical intervention. PPH was most common obstetrical haemorrhage followed by APH. Severe anemia and DIC observed among complication of massive haemorrhage. Early and effective measures to prevent risk factors of obstetric haemorrhage in antepartum and postpartum period certainly affects the maternal outcome positively.

Most of the patients required blood transfusion, ionotrope and ventilatory support.

Maternal mortality in our study was found to be 238 of a total 2139 obs ICU admission i.e. 11.12%. Most common causes of maternal mortality in our study was obstetric haemorrhage (28.57%) followed by HDP (15.55%) and septicaemia (14.28%) which is similar to studies conducted by Rathod et al, Gupta et al. [9,10]

Conclusion

Indian women are mostly dependent on head of the household for their health and fertility related issues. Lack of awareness, socio cultural factors and poverty are major factors contributing it. This leads to delayed seeking of medical care facilities. Delayed referral at primary level and reluctance of patients to reach tertiary centre and hence losing valuable time also contributes to poor outcome. Improving quality of health care facilities and providers and establishment of adequately staffed high functioning obstetric ICU in government tertiary centres are essential for reducing maternal mortality and morbidity.

Acknowledgement: We are grateful to our patients, their attendants and whole obstetric ICU team for their cooperation.

Funding: Nil.

References

1. Dattaray C, Mandal D, Shankar U, Bhattacharya P, Mandal S. Obstetric patients requiring high-dependency unit admission in a tertiary referral centre. *Int J Crit Illn Inj Sci.* 2013 Jan; 3(1):31-5.
2. Adeoye IA, Onayade AA, Fatusi AO. Incidence, determinants and perinatal outcomes of near miss maternal morbidity in Ile-Ife Nigeria: a prospective case control study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2013 Apr 15;13:93.
3. Soubra, S.H. and Guntupalli, K.K. Critical illness in pregnancy: An overview. *Critical Care Medicine,* 2005;33: S248-S255.
4. <https://www.who.int/news/item/30-05-2024-countries-commit-to-recover-lost-progress-in-maternal--newborn---child-survival>
5. [https://www.who.int/data/gho/indicator-met-ad-ata-registry/imrdetails/4622#:~:text=Indirect%20obstetric%20deaths%20\(or%20indirect,the%20physiologic%20effects%20of%20pregnancy%E2%80%9D](https://www.who.int/data/gho/indicator-met-ad-ata-registry/imrdetails/4622#:~:text=Indirect%20obstetric%20deaths%20(or%20indirect,the%20physiologic%20effects%20of%20pregnancy%E2%80%9D).
6. Cochet L, Pattinson RC, MacDonald AP. Severe acute maternal morbidity and maternal death audit—a rapid diagnostic tool for evaluating maternal care. *S Afr Med J.* 2003; 93(9):701–702.
7. Baskett TF. Epidemiology of obstetric critical care. *Best Pract Res Clinic Obstet Gynaecol* 2008;22(5):763–774.
8. International statistical classification of diseases and related health problems. 10th Rev, Vol. 2, World Health Organization, Geneva, 1992; 98-99.
9. Gupta S, Naithani U, Doshi V, Bhargava V, Vijay BS. Obstetric critical care: A prospective analysis of clinical characteristics, predictability, and fetomaternal outcome in a new dedicated obstetric intensive care unit. *Indian J Anaesth.* 2011 Mar;55(2):146-53.
10. Verma D, Rathore AM. Obstetric admissions to the intensive care unit of a tertiary hospital in northern India. *Int J Biomed Res.* 2014; 5(9):539-42.
11. Khan KS, Wojdyla D, Say L, Gulmezoglu AM, Van Look PF. WHO analysis of causes of maternal death: A systematic review. *Lancet.* 2006;367: 1066-74.
12. Bhadade R, de SQ Souza R, More A, Harde M. Maternal outcomes in critically ill obstetrics patients: A unique challenge. *Indian J Crit Care Med* 2012;16:8-16